

ISic3120

I.Sicily inscription 3120

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Seen by Houel

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Φαύλλου Ἐλεάτα

Apparatus

Text of Meligunis Lipára XII

Houel: ΦΑΥΜΟΥ

Translation (en)

(tomb) of Phaullos of Elea

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645461

PHI 334170

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